

EFFECTS OF THERMOFORMING ON THE CELL MORPHOLOGY OF A THERMOPLASTIC CORE

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SUMMARY

Thermoplastic foams are a promising material in applications such as sandwich structures. They reduce processing cycle time, final part price and can be post-processed, mainly by thermoforming. Foaming properties of a foam grade PET were investigated. The foamed cores were then thermoformed and changes induced to cells morphology were evaluated.

Keywords: sandwich, cores, thermoforming, foam morphology, semicrystalline polymer

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric foams are typically employed for a lot of applications such as packaging, thermal and acoustic insulation, and in the impact energy absorption [1, 2]. The growing need to decrease the weight in automotive, transport and aeronautic industries increased the use of foams in light structures, in particular sandwiches, with high flexural strength, high rigidity, good impact strength. Conventional sandwich structures are usually prepared by bonding composite skins to the core through an adhesive layer, but due to several critical issues related to the thermoforming of foamed sheets, thermosetting polymers are commonly employed as cores, thanks to their ability to fill the space when expanding between the previously formed skin layers [3, 4].

Thermoplastic cores are gaining ever more attention due to their strong potential advantages over thermosetting ones: higher productivity, lower raw material cost, recycling, easier welding [5, 6]. Thermoplastics foamed sheets can be thermoformed after the foaming step being deformable at high temperatures. Even if thermoforming process is not difficult to perform on foamed cores, great attention should be paid if a semicrystalline polymer is used [4, 7]. In fact, the presence of crystals enhance the mechanical properties but tends to hinder an adequate flow of macromolecules during forming, inducing residual stresses and strains in the final structure.

In this work a foam grade Poly(ethylene terephthalate), PET was studied. It is a low cost engineering polymer with good mechanical and thermal characteristics, high elastic moduli, glass transition temperature well above room temperature and good crystallinity level [8], and it is characterized by a very high performance/cost ratio.

Several tests were performed on the pristine material to identify the processing condition for foaming. In particular, the crystallization kinetics were evaluated and foaming conditions of semicrystalline PET were investigated. Thermoforming was instead performed on supplied foam sheets. The effects of the thermoforming process on the foam morphology were evaluated by measuring cell morphology before and after the deformation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The foam grade PET (Cobifoam 0) used in this work (intrinsic viscosity of 1.25dl/g, $T_g = 75^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_m = 255^\circ\text{C}$) was kindly supplied by Mossi & Ghisolfi S.p.A.

Isothermal cold and melt crystallization tests were performed in order to define the crystallization kinetics of the PET samples. Samples were first melted at 290°C for 4 minutes in the DSC cell in order to clear the previous thermal history, and then quenched in liquid nitrogen to avoid crystal nucleation. The samples were kept in anhydrous conditions before the isothermal test. For cold crystallization tests the samples were heated at the selected temperature from room temperature, while for melt crystallization experiments the samples were melted at 290°C for 4 minutes and then quickly cooled at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in the DSC cell to the test temperature. All the tests were performed with a TA Instruments DSC 2920.

The foaming behavior was evaluated by means of a batch apparatus. A wide temperature range (from 180 to 250°C) and two solubilization pressures (90 and 165bar) of the blowing agent ($99,95\%$ pure CO_2 , supplied by Rivoira S.p.A.) were used. After melting at 300°C for 5 minutes, the gas was solubilized in the samples for 30 minutes in the polymer at the selected pressure and temperature. Subsequently, the pressure was released to 1 bar in approximately 0,2s and expansion occurred. The morphological properties were evaluated from SEM micrographies, obtained through an electron scanning microscope Leica S440.

Foamed sheets of different thickness (20mm and 45mm) and densities (75 , 109 , 156 kg/m^3) supplied by BC Foam S.p.A. were thermoformed. A custom made mould with a 90° forming angle was used in order to produce planar deformations (L-shape). All samples (70mm wide, 320mm long) were heated at the selected temperature for 10 minutes in an oven and then formed. This process was performed at room temperature by using both a 40mm cylindrical indenter. A 12mm diameter indenter was also used to evaluate the effect of forming diameter on the final shape of sheets. The shapes were then analysed with a stereoscopic optical microscope (Leica APO Z16) and main morphological characteristics were measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crystallization kinetics

In order to produce foams, some tests were performed to evaluate the crystallization kinetics of the semicrystalline polymer. In figure 1 the crystallization behavior of the selected PET is shown (and compared to that of a bottle grade PET, not suitable for foaming). The higher molecular weight of the foam grade PET [9-10] exhibits a lower

crystallization rate, as evident from the lower values of the crystallization rate curve. In particular, the crystallization rate start to be significant at 125°C for cold crystallization process and 209°C from molten state. The peak of the predicted curve, modeled with the Hoffman – Lauritzen [11] equation of crystallization rate, was around 175°C. This means that PET processing at temperature near 175°C should be performed very carefully if the development of crystallinity is a critical issue.

Figure 1. Comparison of crystallization kinetics of foam grade and bottle grade PETs

Foaming process

In figure 2 sample densities obtained with our process are summarized. As evident from the figure, expansion occurred above 190°C, but the use of higher amount of blowing agent and the higher value of foaming pressure gave rise to a less expanded foam at 200°C (expansion ratio lower than 2) when compared to the low pressure sample. Probably the increased amount of solubilized CO₂ enhanced the plasticization effect of the polymeric macromolecules (T_g lowering) and provoked a partial pressure induced crystallization that hindered expansion of the material. At higher temperatures this phenomenon was not present and very low density values were obtained (60kg/m³).

The foam morphology was strongly influenced by processing conditions (Figure 3). The low solubilization pressure allowed to produce foams with small cell diameter (120µm) but as the temperature rose the cell dimension starts to grow up to 240µm at 230°C, keeping the same foam density values. This means that a) the higher temperature induced a coalescence of the cell and/or b) the lower degree of undercooling induced a lower amount of nucleated cells. For higher solubilization pressure the cell diameter was approximately constant with the temperature (about 100µm). This was related to the higher depressurization rate, that directly affected the nucleation rate.

At temperatures higher than 230°C was not possible to produce foams with an homogeneous and regular morphology by means of CO₂ because of the low viscosity of the polymer and the coalescence of cells during the cell growth.

Figure 2. Foam densities as function of expansion temperature and solubilization pressure

Figure 3. SEM micrographies of foams obtained at low and high pressure level

Thermoforming

Thermoforming tests were performed on foamed sheets a) to evaluate the minimum thermoforming temperature that was suitable to induce an L-shape to samples and b) to investigate the effects of deformations on the cellular morphology after process. Unfortunately, the supplied PET sheets were completely crystallized. This was the reason of the springback evidenced by quite all samples (figure 4). Different thermoforming temperatures were employed and the minimum temperature to induce a square angle was found to be 160°C (85°C higher than the T_g).

In Table 1 the values of the spring-back angle are reported for the 20mm thick sheets and 40mm diameter indenter. When the 12mm diameter indenter was used to thermoform sheets, the L-shape was easily obtained at 160°C, with a reduced curvature radius of the external surface. The drawback of this tool was the contact surface with foam sheet, smaller than the contact surface of the 40mm tool. In this conditions the cellular structure was permanently indented, in particular for the lower density sheet. This results suggest that the indenter diameter/sheet thickness ratio should be related to the foam density and taken into account during the design of the thermoforming apparatus. Some authors proposed an apparatus to assist the thermoforming of a thermoplastic foamed sheet and strongly reduced the tool indentation [5].

Table 1. Spring-back angle values

Temperature [°C]	Density [kg/m ³]		
	75	109	156
130	25	-	26
140	30	20	21
150	9	20	26
160	4	0	3
160 (small diam.)	6	0	3
160 (high thick.)	15	10	8
175	3	0	2

Figure 4. Thermoformed sections of foamed PET sheets as function of the forming temperature and indenter diameter

At 160°C the 45mm thick sheets showed a significant spring-back after forming. This was addressed to the inhomogeneous heating of the inner volume of samples, which needed a longer heating time.

In order to show the effects of thermoforming on the cellular morphology, two samples for each foam density, formed at 160°C and 175°C, were optically analysed and the results were compared to the undeformed one. The thermoforming process induced a variation on the cell morphology along sheet thickness and, in particular, deformed cells in the inner and outer layers, respectively compressing and stretching zones, are clearly evidenced in figures 5-7.

The cell aspect ratio of the undeformed sample, approximately 1, was constant in the section, but thermoforming produced at all temperatures an aspect ratio gradient in the radial (thermoforming) direction, inducing a variation of the cell morphology along the thickness. The foam cells in the internal surface were compressed in the radial direction (aspect ratio > 1), while outer cells were stretched in the tangential direction (aspect ratio < 1). The internal zone micrography (taken from the internal radius, left images of each of the following figures) shows a reduction of the cell width in the tangential direction, while the outer zone micrography (taken from the external radius, right images of each of the following figures) shows a compression in the radial direction.

Some experiments were performed for each foam density to investigate the shape stability with temperature. This analysis pointed out that the internal and external cells were in a metastable state due to the complete crystallization of polymer before forming. As the temperature approximate the glass transition temperature, a strong springback effect took place due to the stress relaxation of the polymeric matrix. This could induce, in a sandwich structure, strong residual stresses. An accurate control of

foaming process during sheet production is needed to avoid crystallization before thermoforming process. The crystalline phase development should only be induced after the sheet shaping, to stabilize the structure and to guarantee adequate mechanical performances at temperatures near and above T_g .

Figure 5. Optical micrographies of undeformed (A) and thermoformed (B) at 160°C 75kg/m³ foams (for B: left, center and right images represents respectively the internal, central and outer zones of the L-shaped sample sections)

Figure 6. Optical micrographies of undeformed (A) and thermoformed (B for 160°, C for 175°C) 109 kg/m³ foams (for B and C: left, center and right images represents respectively the internal, central and outer zones of the L-shaped sample sections)

Furthermore, data in Table 2 suggest that the neutral stress plane could be different from the geometric middle plane. In order to be coincident, the aspect ratio values of the central zones should be near 1 but in our case they were less than 1. The neutral stress plane is shifted towards the inner surface and this behavior is more pronounced at 175°C.

Figure 7. Optical micrographies of undeformed (A) and thermoformed (B for 160°, C for 175°C) 156 kg/m³ foams (for B and C: left, center and right images represents respectively the internal, central and outer zones of the L-shaped sample sections)

Table 2. Aspect ratios of cells in undeformed (UN) and thermoformed (TF) foams at different temperatures

<i>Foam Density [kg/m³]</i>	<i>75</i>		<i>109</i>			<i>156</i>		
Position	UN	TF (160°C)	UN	TF (160°C)	TF (175°C)	UN	TF (160°C)	TF (175°C)
Internal	0,97	1,45	1,02	1,15	1,26	0,97	1,47	1,45
Central	0,96	0,99	0,99	0,74	0,85	0,94	0,90	1,04
External	0,96	0,83	0,98	0,68	0,47	0,92	0,86	0,53

The aspect ratio gradient was also influenced by the the forming temperature. The higher thermoforming temperature induced a stronger stretching of cells on the outer layer, as resulted from the lower aspect ratios in Table 2.

CONCLUSIONS

A thermoplastic semicrystalline core for sandwich structures, based on a foam grade PET, was investigated in this work. The foaming conditions and crystallization kinetics were studied in order to define the main parameters influencing its foam processing and thermoforming.

The crystallization rate curve was calculated from cold and melt isothermal crystallization experiments. The data were used to select the temperatures suitable for batch foaming and were related to the thermoforming results.

The effects on cellular structure of the physical blowing agent (carbon dioxide) solubilization pressure and of processing conditions (foaming temperatures) were clarified. Foams with density as low as 60kg/m³ were produced. The use of higher solubilization pressure induced a finer morphology at every foaming temperature when

compared to the low pressure process at every temperature, probably due to the stronger influence of the higher thermodynamical instability on cell nucleation.

Foamed sheets, characterized by different densities, were thermoformed. The minimum processing temperature for obtaining L-shapes was found and the resulting morphology was investigated and measured. Thermoformed samples exhibited an aspect ratio gradient along the sheet thickness, more pronounced for higher thermoforming temperature. The internal cells were compressed (aspect ratio > 1) while the outer cells were stretched (aspect ratio < 1).

An important springback effect was also evidenced by many samples due to the high crystallinity of supplied PET sheets, both at low thermoforming temperatures and after reheating above T_g .

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